

WOMEN

SLOVENIA MAY 2011

TODAY'S

ON THIS ISSUE
CONTENT ANALYSIS OF
BRAZILIAN AFRO-DESCENDANT
WOMEN PORTRAIT ON PRINTED
ADVERTISEMENTS

BY LUIZ VALÉRIO DE PAULA TRINDADE &
CLAUDIA ROSA ACEVEDO CAMPANARIO

ABSTRACT

THIS IS A CONTENT ANALYSIS STUDY ON 660 ADS OUT OF 46 MAGAZINES OF THREE CATEGORIES (BUSINESS, GENERAL INTEREST AND FEMININE) AIMED AT EXAMINING THE FREQUENCY AND PORTRAYAL OF BRAZILIAN AFRO-DESCENDANT WOMEN. IT HAS REVEALED A LARGE UNDERREPRESENTATION OF FEMALE AFRO-DESCENDANT INDIVIDUALS, GREAT ASYMMETRY BETWEEN ETHNIC GROUPS ON THE COUNTRY'S INHABITANTS AND THEIR PRESENCE ON ADVERTISEMENTS AND THAT ADS FAIL TO CONVEY AN INCLUSIVE VIEW OF BRAZILIAN SOCIETY.

KEY-WORDS: GENDER; SOCIAL INVISIBILITY; ADVERTISEMENTS; STEREOTYPES; AFRO-DESCENDANT

INTRODUCTION

In the recent past there has been a growing influx of women in the work market and alongside this phenomenon, new perspectives have also arise for them. Consequently, nowadays it is not uncommon to find women on positions where previously were occupied solely for men and they have also been playing an increasing variety of social roles (Cappelle et al, 2002). However, besides this fact, it can be noticed that women also face a variety of challenges. The beauty industry, for example, have established and disseminated a so called beauty pattern that most women should fit themselves in order to feel socially accepted or physically attractive to men. Such profile portrayed on countless magazine covers and advertisements is usually made up of a tall woman, thin body, white skin complexion, blond hair and clear eyes, as described by Redmond (2003), and this situation lays a great pressure on women shoulders of all ethnic groups in general.

Nevertheless, for non-white women, the challenges to cope with this scenario tends to be even bigger. Chadha (2007), for instance, reports that in India, the clearer the skin of a person is, the more attractive or good-looking he/she becomes in that society, in such a way that the country's skin-lightening cream industry turnover surpass US\$ 190 million. Besides that, Chadha (2007) also adds that in India "most advertisements for the [whitening] cream tend to portray that a dark skin will hold a person back, whereas fair skin will mean social acceptance and even success in the chosen profession, as well as among the opposite sex". In the U.S. for example, Hunt (2007, p. 16) calls attention to the fact that it has become "increasingly difficult for Latina, African-American, Asian and South-Asian models to get runway work" due to a decline in ethnic diversity in this area. Hunt

(2007, p. 17) also argues that runways made up of groups of entirely white and blond models conveys a subtle message to "consumers, aspiring models and young girls alike that certain groups of people are more valuable than others". That way, Hunt (2007) says, young girls of non-white ethnic origins have few or no role models to inspire from.

On the other hand, the Brazilian afro-descendant women face firstly a professional devaluation, in such a way that according to Quadros (2004, p. 96), on average, they earn only 31.1% of a white man wage, while white women earn 62.2% of a white man wage. Besides that, as pointed out by Corrêa (2006), advertisements usually portray afro-descendant women highlighting mainly their sexy attributes instead of other consumer possibilities. Oliveira; Pavan (2005, p. 4) say that this bond is so strong within people minds in Brazil that a successful soap opera broadcasted in 2004 on a leading TV channel that had an afro-descendant female character in the leading role was named "The Sin Color", characterizing the sinful aspect of black sensuality.

It can be noticed that media products and means of mass communication in general play an important role on modern society given the fact that they can create, spread and reinforce social roles through their messages conveyed onto society. According to Kang (1997), advertisements give meaning to words and symbols and as such it plays a special role in the interpretation frame of the current world. Cappelle et al (2002) and Hazell; Clarck (2008) argue that media plays a role of great relevance both on the creation as well as on the reinforcement of social representations, considering the fact that through them social groups get recognition, visibility and reinforcement of their identity. Moreover, Bristor;

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF BRAZILIAN AFRO-DESCENDANT WOMEN PORTRAIT ON PRINTED ADVERTISEMENTS

Lee; Hunt (1995, p. 48) also point out that the lack of diversity on advertisements and the inaccuracy on the way they portray ethnic minorities have a negative impact on them because they “tend to reflect white’s attitudes toward minorities and, therefore, reveal more about whites themselves than about the varied and lived experiences of minorities”. Additionally, it is also possible to notice that Humphrey; Schuman (1984, p. 563) share a similar thought when they argue that “advertisers usually portray white individuals on the way they think about themselves and negroes as white think of them”. When it comes to portray ethnic minorities, it is possible to notice that advertisements do not have an inclusive view of the Brazilian society. The more it portrays individuals on the same way, the more the ethnic minority tends to have their social possibilities shortened and, consequently, they will have to fit themselves onto models diverse from their own cultural background in order to become socially accepted.

Although minorities groups have been on the rise in many countries on what regards their number and mainly the diversity of their social roles, as pointed out by Williams; Lee; Haugtvedt (2004), Jedwab (2006), Pornsakulvanich (2007); Trindade (2008) and Sirkeci (2009), there is still a lack of ethnic diversity in advertising on many countries. Besides that, Baker; Gentry; Rittenburg (2005, p. 137) also argue that “the majority of empirical research in marketing and consumer behavior has focused on middle-class Caucasian consumers”. Therefore it is considered that expanding the boundaries and looking at consumers who are not necessarily part of the mainstream allows increasing the understanding and knowledge of the impact and the consequences of marketing message onto society as a whole and on the

disadvantaged minority groups in particular, such as afro-descendant women. Hence, the key research question of the present study lays on the following point: investigate the frequency and how afro-descendant women are portrayed on printed pieces of advertisements in Brazil. For that purpose, the study will conduct a **content analysis on 660 advertisements out of 46 large circulation magazines of three categories (general interest, business and feminine).**

The importance and relevance of this study is justified by the fact that it covers three aspects: 1) it deals with a subject matter of interest to many research groups both in Brazil and abroad (such as: Núcleo Negro da Unesp para Pesquisa e Extensão-Brazil; Marketing Ethnic Faculty Association – USA; Ethnic Marketing Group – University of Cardiff-UK; Centre for Research in Equality and Diversity – Queen Mary University of London; Centre for Research in Advertising and Consumption – University of Bath-UK; Center for Consumer Equality – University of Texas at Austin); 2) it address issues of creation, reinforcement and diffusion of stigmas and stereotypes regarding afro-descendant women on means of mass communication; 3) it discuss about an expressive portion of Brazilian population that has shown clear evidences of increasing purchasing power along the recent past and, consequently, it represents an unexplored market with significant consumption potential.

The study is divided into four parts, being the first one covering the introduction, the research question, relevance and justification of the study. The second part presents the literature review about the subject matter, followed by the research method and the results. Finally, the fourth part, address the discussion about the results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Brazilian society has experienced a process of increasing social mobility that has allowed a greater number of afro-descendant individuals ascend socially and achieve greater purchasing power (Jones, 2004). According to Pinheiro (2008), afro-descendant individuals make up 48.5% of Brazilian population, whereas white individuals represent 50.6% and the remaining 0.96% is made up of individuals of other ethnic origins. However, on what concerns the presence of afro-descendant individuals in general on printed advertisements it is usually lower than 10% and, in many cases, their portrayals does not reflect their present social roles (Jones, 2004; Corrêa, 2006; Trindade, 2008).

The over exposition of one ethnic group and the devaluation of others in such way that the second group is influenced to fit into the dominant model, as described by Chadha (2007); Hunt (2007); Corrêa (2006) and Trindade (2008), keeps conceptual similarity with the Established and Outsiders theory due to the fact that the first group self-proclaim itself as the standard group while calls the others as outsiders (Elias; Scotson, 2000). Moreover, the greater the exposition and over-valuation of the established group, the greater its cohesion as a group and also the greater the desire of the outsiders to comply with such pattern in order to be accepted (Elias; Scotson, 2000).

It can also be noticed that there are many studies addressing the issue of afro-descendant individuals as a group on means of mass communication in general on Brazilian academic literature. Nevertheless, on what regards previous research addressing specifically the portrayal of Brazilian afro-descendant women on means of mass communication it is possible to notice that there is not much history on that field.

During the literature review for the present study it was possible to find works of Silva (1998); Custódio (2005); Silva (2005); Strozenberg (2006) and Christo (2009). On the international literature, the picture does not differ that much and it was possible to identify studies carried out by Bristor; Lee; Hunt (1995); Patton (2001); Frisby (2004); Davis (2007); Hazell; Clarke (2008) and Covert; Dixon (2008).

The review of the mentioned studies allows us to identify that Silva (1998) developed a research about the portrayal of afro-descendant women on magazines directed toward afro-descendant individuals. Silva (1998) argues that those magazines are shallow and replicate the model found on other mainstream publications and devote more room to present how-to articles (such as, how to become beautiful inside-out, how to make your skin perfect and soft in winter, and so on) and neglect subjects such as the social condition of afro-descendant women for example.

Custódio (2005) on her turn, has developed a study on two mainstream feminine magazines (Cláudia and Nova) between 1980 and 1996 in order to identify the presence of afro-descendant women on advertisements and she has found out that their presence alongside that timeframe has not exceed 2.5%.

The study carried out by Silva (2005) has somehow confirmed the conclusions of the previous ones and stated that the presence of such individuals is modest. Besides that, this author also mentions that the low visibility of this social group is largely influenced by the country's cultural history of over 300 years of slavery. Silva (2005) also sheds light to the fact that progresses have occurred on what regards a recent larger presence of afro-descendant women on advertisements, however, this is due mainly to government initiatives and organized civil rights movements, than a voluntary movement from the advertisers.

On the other hand, Strozenberg (2006) presents a more positive perspective on this issue and, according to her, there has been progresses on the representation of afro-descendant individuals on advertisements. Contrary to the previous mentioned studies, Strozenberg (2006) does not presents numbers to back up her arguments, however, she points out that due to a recent increase in the presence of afro-descendant models on publications, this phenomenon has contributed to a slight shift into the established aesthetic Caucasian paradigm toward a more diversified one.

Slightly different from those studies, Christo (2009) conducted a research assessing the identity construction of male and female afro-descendent individuals through the pages of Raça Brasil (the country's main magazine directed toward afro-descendant community).

The author explains that the reasoning behind this study lays in the fact that being the only magazine with this profile it was expected that it would also represent a favorable ground to convey a more appropriate picture of afro-descendant individuals. However, according to Christo (2009), the research found out that it just replicates the same profiles of male and female afro-descendant individuals already found on mainstream magazines.

On what regards the international studies, Bristor; Lee; Hunt (1995) argue that means of mass communication can convey racial prejudice by a varied of ways and among them it can be highlighted: a) omission; b) maintenance of stereotypes and repeatedly portraying those individuals negatively and usually associated with low qualifications social roles. Moreover, Bristor; Lee; Hunt (1995) also add that the problem does not lay on the degree of accuracy of the portrayals but much more on the lack of balance between the ethnic groups portrayed.

Through Complicity Theory, Standpoint Feminist and Womanism, Patton (2001) analyzed a popular U.S. TV show named Ally McBeal in order to assess how women and ethnic minorities are stereotypically portrayed on such media product. Patton's (2001) study suggests that media in general keeps on portraying stereotypes of ethnic minorities, over expose Caucasian individuals and fail to promote a more equality human experience.

Just like Redmond (2003) who has examined the idealized images of thin white women on British women's magazines, Frisby (2004) has made use of the Theory of Social Comparison in order to study the impact on afro-American women's self-esteem caused by such Caucasian models on advertisements and countless magazine covers. In summary, Frisby (2004) has identified that similar characters portrayed on advertisements make it easier for afro-American women establish a rapport than when exposed solely to out-group members.

On her turn, Davis (2007) has made use of the Collective Memory Theory in order to study different perspectives regarding advertising of a well-known brand in the U.S. called Aunt Jemina. As the Collective Memory Theory is a sociological construct that explains how members of different social groups recall the past, Davis (2007, p. 30) has shown that Aunt Jemina's image would probably represent diverse symbols and meanings to white and afro-American audiences. Given that fact, the author argues that the advertisers have taken that into consideration and created a campaign that did not recall into people's mind images of stereotyped afro-American women.

Through a content analysis on advertisements in two magazines directed toward afro-American individuals,

Hazell; Clarke (2008) have examined their portrait on such ads. The authors have identified that the two magazines studied (Essence and Jet) have revealed a significant improvement on both the frequency of afro-American characters as well as on the quality of the roles played. However, Hazell; Clarke (2008) also warn that as importantly as this fact, there must also occur a decrease on negative and stereotypical portrait of such individuals on advertisements in order to wipe off society ideology and belief of White supremacy concerning race and gender.

Finally, Covert; Dixon (2008) have developed a content analysis on 10 mainstream U.S. magazines in order to examine the representation of afro-American women on those magazine's content over two time periods (1999 and 2004). The authors have conducted two studies within the same article and firstly, Covert; Dixon (2008) have found out that, when compared to the U.S. Census, afro-American and Latina women were greatly underrepresented on the magazines assessed whereas Caucasian women were overrepresented. On the other hand, as Covert; Dixon (2008) have analyzed the issue along two time periods, they have also identified that there has been a positive trend on the increasing participation of afro-American women on the recent past, even though they still lag well behind white women.

METHOD AND RESULTS

On what regards the methodological procedures of the present study, it was supported by criteria found on similar previous researches such as Kassarian (1969), Cox (1970), Humprey; Schuman (1984), Hazell; Clarke (2008) and Covert; Dixon (2008).

The sampling was made up of 46 large circulation Brazilian mainstream magazines (Chart 01) of three categories published in 2006. Within this study, the term mainstream refers to leading magazines with a large readership and national coverage. That way, the sampling was composed of the following publications:

VEJA: this general interest magazine is published since 1968 on a weekly basis and it has become the country's largest readership magazine;

PEGN: a monthly business magazine published since 1988 and it deals solely with entrepreneurship issues;

EXAME: published since 1967 on a fortnight basis, it has become one of the country's most important and influential business magazine;

NOVA: launched in 1973 as a franchise of the U.S. Cosmopolitan magazine, it is published monthly and it address issues such as love relationship, lifestyle, fashion, career, beauty, women health, sex issues and so on;

CLÁUDIA: published monthly since 1961 it is one of the oldest magazine in circulation in Brazil and it is also the main feminine publication holding the largest readership on its category. While Nova is focused on young adult women, this one is directed toward the more mature ones, since it covers issues such as marriage, family, raising kids, family finances and many others.

CHART 01: MAGAZINES DETAILS AND RESULTS OF THE ETHNIC GROUPS PARTICIPATION

Category	Publication	Absolute Values				Relative Values				Advertisements	Magazines	Readership
		Afro-descendant	White	Other Ethnicity	Total	Afro-descendant	White	Other Ethnicity	Total			
General Interest	Veja	6	86	2	94	6.38%	91.49%	2.13%	100%	111	11	1,085,260
Business	PEGN	10	52	3	65	15.38%	80%	4.62%	100%	76	11	150,000
	Exame	11	72	4	87	12.64%	82.76%	4.6%	100%	101	12	171,330
Feminine	Nova	8	152	1	161	4.97%	94.41%	0.62%	100%	152	5	235,860
	Cláudia	8	227	2	237	3.38%	95.78%	0.84%	100%	220	7	410,170
Total		43	589	12	644	6.68%	91.46%	1.86%	100%	660	46	2,052,620
Census (year 2006)						48.5%	50.6%	0.9%	100%			
Percentage Point Differential						-41.82	40.86%	0.96%				

Source: developed by the authors based on IBGE (2010) and content analysis on magazines | Note: for 2006; $\chi^2 (3, n = 644) = 451,38; p = 95\%$

DISCUSSION AND FINAL CO

The aim of the study was to investigate the frequency and the way Brazilian afro-descendant women are portrayed on magazine advertisements. Similarly to previous researches, the results have revealed a large underrepresentation of this ethnic group when compared to white female individuals.

The over exposition of one ethnic group over others resembles the principles of the Theory of Established and Outsiders (Elias; Scotson, 2000) taken into account that the dominant group portray themselves as the standard individual while others are considered outsiders who should strive to comply with the established pattern. However, this process of over exposition of one ethnic group shadowing others can lead them to deny their own ethnic identity or devaluate their own characteristics, as described by Chadha (2007) and Trindade (2008). Even though the focus of the

was directed toward Brazilian afro-descendant women, the research has revealed that the phenomenon of underrepresentation of this ethnic group is not restricted to a single nation and it can be also found on other cultural contexts such as, for instance, in India (Chadha, 2007) and in the U.S. (Hunt, 2007; Covert; Dixon, 2008).

That way, the challenges faced by ethnic minorities women in general, and afro-descendant female individuals in particular, are huge due to the fact that advertisements keep on almost ignoring their presence on society or not keeping up with their increasing and diversified social roles. Besides that, as argued by Bristor; Lee; Hunt (1995, p. 48) the lack of diversity on advertisements causes a negative impact on the underrepresented groups because it "tends to reflect white's attitudes toward minorities and, therefore,

Similarly to Kassarjian (1969) and Taylor; Landreth; Bang (2005) the present study has made use of two judges in order to collect the data out of the 46 magazines for the content analysis. This group of magazines has 660 advertisements of interest to the research. Those ads of each magazine were coded within three categories in order to examine afro-descendant women representation on them:

1. Character relevance: it was identified whether the character was portrayed on a main role, secondary role or background role;
2. The character age group: child, young/teenager, adult or elderly;
3. Type of product advertised: durable goods, non-durable goods or services.

The results reveal that 91.46% of the women portrayed on the magazines advertisements were white, while 6.68% of them were afro-descendant and 1.86% were of other ethnic origins. This picture confirms similar previous studies (Jones, 2004; Custódio, 2005; Corrêa, 2006; Trindade, 2008; Covert; Dixon, 2008) on the sense that it reveals a large underrepresentation of afro-descendant individuals on magazine ads. Additionally, the overrepresentation of white female on this media product is a phenomenon similar to Elias; Scotson's (2000) Theory of Established and Outsiders as previously discussed on the Literature Review.

Similarly to Covert; Dixon (2008) it has been conducted a comparison between the participation of the different ethnic groups on advertisements and their respective presence on Brazil's population measured by the official Census. Through Chart 01 it is possible to notice that while the percentage

point differential regarding white women is positive on 40.86%, on the other hand on what concerns afro-descendant women it is negative on 41.82%. On other words, the country's official Census shows a relative balance between the two ethnic groups but on advertisements afro-descendant women are practically neglected or ignored as a consumer.

Moreover, it is also interesting to notice the fact that feminine magazines (Nova and Cláudia) convey the lowest rate of afro-descendant women on advertisements (both below 5%) while business publications (PEGN and Exame) hold the highest ones (both above 10%).

On what concerns the representation of afro-descendant women it was possible to notice that white female is predominantly portrayed on main role (the lowest rate was 80% on PEGN magazine and the highest 99.08% on Cláudia), while afro-descendant women are portrayed more on secondary roles than on main roles on three magazines (Veja, Exame and Cláudia).

The study also reveals a larger proportion of child afro-descendant character (on Veja, PEGN, Exame and Nova) than adults, whereas white female character on this situation is observed only twice (PEGN and Cláudia).

Finally, as the presence of white female character is much larger than other ethnic groups, there is also a greater balance on the type of product advertised by them on the majority of the magazines. On the other hand, afro-descendant women are more prone to be characterized on advertisements of services (PEGN, Nova and Cláudia).

CONSIDERATIONS

reveal more about whites themselves than about a varied and lived experiences of minorities". Additionally, the study has also revealed that on what concerns the representation of women on advertisements, there is also a large overrepresentation of white individuals on leading roles, whereas afro-descendant female individuals are more prone to be represented on secondary roles or background roles. So that, this scenario reinforces the concept of social invisibility of minority groups as argued by Silva (2005). Accordingly, the present research indicates that when it comes to portray ethnic minorities female groups, pieces of advertisements do not convey an inclusive view of society and, due to this fact, those underrepresented groups tends to have their social possibilities shortened and, consequently, they are influenced to fit themselves onto models diverse from their own cultural background in order to become socially accepted.

REFERENCES

- :: Baker, S. M.; Gentry, J. W.; Rittenburg, T. L. Building understanding of the domain of consumer vulnerability. *Journal of Macromarketing*. v. 25, n. 2, December 2005, pp. 128-139
- :: Bristor, J. M.; Lee, R. G.; Hunt, M. Race and ideology: African-American images in television advertising. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*. Spring 1995, vol. 14 (1), pp. 48-59
- :: Capelle, M. C. A. et al. A representação feminina na mídia de negócios: um estudo com duas revistas populares especializadas em gestão. *XVII EnAnpad*, 2002
- :: Chadha, M. Indian men go tall, fair and handsome. *BBC News*. Available at: http://news.bbc.co.uk/go/pr/fr/-/2/hi/south_asia/4396122.stm (Retrieved on 25th September, 2007)
- :: Christo, B. L. G. O. *Homens e mulheres da "Raça": uma análise discursiva da construção da identidade negra na revista Raça Brasil*. Monograph (Bachelor in Journalism). Universidade Federal de Viçosa, MG, 2009
- :: Corrêa, L. G. *De corpo presente: o negro na publicidade em revista*. Dissertation (MPhil in Communication Science) - Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais. Belo Horizonte, MG, 2006
- :: Covert, J. J.; Dixon, T. L. A Changing View: Representation and Effects of the Portrayal of Women of Color in Mainstream Women's Magazines. *Communication Research*. vol. 35, n. 2, April 2008, pp. 232-256
- :: Cox, K. K. Social effects of integrated advertising. *Journal of Advertising Research*. vol. 10, n. 2, April 1970, pp. 41-44
- :: Custódio, M. S. Mulher negra: da inserção na história a inserção na propaganda. *Revista de Iniciação Científica da FFC*. 2005, vol. 5, n. 1/2/3, pp. 37-49
- :: Davis, J. F. "Aunt Jemima is Alive and Cookin'?" An Advertiser's Dilemma of Competing Collective Memories. *Journal of Macromarketing*. vol. 27, n. 1, March 2007, pp. 25-37
- :: Elias, N.; Scotson, J. *Os estabelecidos e os outsiders*. Rio de Janeiro: Jorge Zahar Editor, 2000, 224 pp.
- :: Frisby, C. M. Does Race Matter?: Effects of Idealized Images on African American Women's Perceptions of Body Esteem. *Journal of Black Studies*. vol. 34, n. 3, January 2004, pp. 323-347
- :: Hazell, V.; Clarke, J. Race and Gender in the Media: A Content Analysis of Advertisements in Two Mainstream Black Magazines. *Journal of Black Studies*. vol. 39, n. 1, September 2008, pp. 5-21
- :: Humprey, R.; Schuman, H. The portrayal of blacks in magazine advertisements: 1950-1982. *Public Opinion Quarterly*. v. 48, n. 3, Fall 1984, pp. 551-563
- :: Hunt, K. The great white way. *Metro Newspaper*. New York, 05th September 2007, pp. 16-17
- :: *Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatísticas - IBGE*. População: Censos Demográficos. Available at: www.ibge.gov.br (Retrieved on 15/01/2010)
- :: Jedwab, J. Ethnic marketing in Canada: the challenges ahead. *Canadian Diversity Magazine*. August 29th, 2006
- :: Jones, V. Espetáculo das raças. *RAE Executivo-FGV*. vol. 3, n. 2, May-July 2004, pp. 31-35
- :: Kang, M. The portrayal of women's images in magazine advertisements: Goffman's gender analysis revisited. *Sex Roles*. New York, December 1997, v. 37, n. 11/12, pp. 979-997
- :: Kassarjian, H. H. The negro and American advertising: 1946-1965. *Journal of Marketing Research*. vol. 11 (February 1969), pp. 29-39
- :: Oliveira, D.; Pavan, M. A. Identificações e estratégias nas relações étnicas na telenovela "Da cor do pecado". *IV Encontro dos Núcleos de Pesquisa da Intercom*, 2005
- :: Patton, T. O. Ally McBeal and Her Homies: The Reification of White Stereotypes of the Other. *Journal of Black Studies*. vol. 32, n. 2, November 2001, pp. 229-260
- :: Pinheiro, L. et al. *Retrato das desigualdades de gênero e raça*. 2008, 3ª ed., IPEA. Brasília, pp. 36
- :: Pornsakulvanich, V. Television portrayals of ethnic minorities in the United States: the analysis of individual differences, media use and group identity and vitality. *ABAC Journal*. vol. 27, n. 3, September-December 2007, pp. 22-28
- :: Quadros, W. Gênero e raça na desigualdade social brasileira recente. *Estudos Avançados*. 18 (50), 2004, pp. 95-117
- :: Redmond, S. Thin White Women in Advertising: Deathly Corporeality. *Journal of Consumer Culture*. 2003, vol. 3(2): 170-190
- :: Silva, C. A. Gênero e identidade na publicidade brasileira. XXVIII Congresso Brasileiro de Ciências da Comunicação. Rio de Janeiro, RJ. 05 a 09 de setembro, 2005
- :: Silva, E. M. Retratos de mulher: a mulher negra nas revistas para o público negro - Estudo de caso. *XXI Intercom*, 1998, Recife
- :: Sirkeci, I. Ethnic marketing potential in England and Wales: new evidences from the 2001 UK Census. *Asian Journal of Marketing*, 2008, 2(1): 1-9
- :: Strozenberg, I. Branca, preta, híbrida: qual é a cor da beleza na propaganda brasileira hoje? *Revista Eletrônica de Jornalismo Científico*. n. 78, julho 2006
- :: Taylor, C. R.; Landreth, S.; Bang, H.. Asian Americans in magazine advertising: portrayals of the "model minority". *Journal of Macromarketing*, vol. 25, n. 2, December 2005, pp. 163-174
- :: Trindade, L. V. P.. *Participação e representação social de indivíduos afro-descendentes retratados em anúncios publicitários de revistas: 1968-2006*. Dissertation (MPhil in Business Administration) - Universidade Nove de Julho, Brazil, 2008
- :: Williams, J. D.; Lee, W.; Haugtvedt, C. P. *Diversity in advertising: broadening the scope of research directions*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Inc., 2004, New Jersey, USA.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS:

LUIZ VALÉRIO DE PAULA TRINDADE

MSc in Business Administration

Universidade Nove de Julho

São Paulo, Brazil

CLAUDIA ROSA ACEVEDO CAMPANARIO

PhD in Business Administration (FGV-SP)

Assistant Professor | Universidade Nove de Julho

São Paulo, Brazil